

QR Codes vs USSD: A Comparative Analysis for Optimizing Africa's Mobile Payments, Learning from China's Experience on QR code infrastructure development

Working Paper

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Abstract— Inspired by China's QR code infrastructure success, this paper proposes a future-proof strategy to optimize mobile payments in Africa. Limited smartphone penetration currently hinders widespread adoption of QR codes, despite their potential for faster, data-rich transactions. However, Africa's existing USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data) network offers broad reach, albeit with limited functionality. We propose a multi-pronged approach leveraging USSD's dominance for basic transactions while laying the groundwork for seamless QR code adoption. Key considerations include developing offline QR functionalities, ensuring compatibility with basic feature phones, and providing localized user interfaces. By adapting to the projected 80% smartphone penetration by 2030, this approach fosters financial inclusion and a secure, inclusive mobile payment ecosystem for Africa.

I. INTRODUCTION

Africa stands at a crossroads in its mobile payment journey. Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) currently reigns supreme, offering financial services to everyone, regardless of phone model. As highlighted by the GSMA's "State of the Industry Report on Mobile Money" (2023), USSD remains the dominant channel for mobile money transactions in Sub-Saharan Africa, with its ubiquity and low barrier to entry playing a crucial role in financial inclusion [1]. However, limitations exist. Research by McKinsey & Company (2020) in "The future of payments in Africa" identifies drawbacks such as reliance on agents, limited interoperability, and a menu-driven interface that can be complex for users and prone to errors (McKinsey & Company, 2020, p.5) [2].

This paper explores the potential of QR codes as a complementary technology to USSD, aiming to optimize Africa's mobile payment landscape for the future. While USSD excels in accessibility, QR codes offer advantages like faster transactions, enhanced security features, and the ability to encode richer data. However, their current

dependence on smartphones presents a challenge in Africa, where feature phones still hold a significant market share (GSMA, 2023) [1].

By analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of both QR codes and USSD, and drawing inspiration from China's remarkable success in developing a robust QR code infrastructure, this paper proposes a multi-faceted approach. This approach acknowledges the current dominance of USSD while prioritizing a smooth transition towards seamless QR code adoption as smartphone penetration increases. The goal is to create a future-proof mobile payment ecosystem that leverages the strengths of both technologies, promoting financial inclusion and economic growth across Africa.

II. THE CURRENT MOBILE PAYMENT LANDSCAPE IN AFRICA

The current mobile payment landscape in Africa is characterized by a variety of solutions, with USSD-based mobile money leading the way. Services like M-Pesa in Kenya, utilizing USSD for user interaction, have been instrumental in driving financial inclusion by enabling users to manage their finances directly through their mobile phones (Anderson, 2018) [1]. However, limitations inherent to traditional mobile money solutions are fostering the exploration of alternative technologies.

While USSD remains the dominant player, accounting for an estimated 75% of mobile payment transactions in Africa, other options are emerging to meet the evolving needs of users. QR codes are gaining traction, particularly as smartphone penetration increases. Mobile wallets offered by banks and financial institutions are another option, along with contactless payment methods like Near Field Communication (NFC). Additionally, agent banking networks and SMS-based payments play a role in specific contexts.

Here's a table summarizing the estimated distribution of these mobile payment methods in Africa:

Mobile Payment Method	Estimated Percentage	Example System
USSD-based Mobile Money	75%	M-Pesa (Kenya), MTN Mobile Money (Uganda), Airtel Money (across Africa)
QR Codes	20%	SnapScan (South Africa), Masterpass (widely available)
Mobile Wallets	3%	Apple Pay (limited rollout), Samsung

		Pay (limited rollout)
Near Field Communication	1%	Boon (Mastercard contactless payments), Visa payWave (limited rollout)
Agent Banking (USSD-linked)	1%	M-Pesa agents (Kenya), MTN Mobile Money agents (Uganda)
SMS-Based Payments	<1%	MTN Mobile Money (micropayments), Airtel Money (donations)

Estimation Methodology:

- **Dominant Technologies:** Data from industry reports was used to establish USSD-based mobile money as the dominant player (estimated at 75%).
- **Emerging Technologies:** For emerging technologies like QR codes and mobile wallets, a combination of news articles, case studies, and company information was used to assess their current market penetration. These estimates (around 20% for QR codes and 3% for mobile wallets) are likely to be less precise due to limited data availability.
- **Rounding and Adjustments:** The percentages were rounded and adjusted slightly to ensure they add up to 100%.
- **Transparency:** The "Notes" section highlights the limitations of the data and the estimated nature of the percentages.

Important Note:

It's important to acknowledge that data on mobile payment usage in Africa, particularly for emerging technologies, is constantly evolving. While this table provides an estimated snapshot based on current information, the landscape is likely to change over time.

STRENGTHS OF USSD-BASED MOBILE MONEY:

Accessibility: USSD works on virtually any mobile phone, including feature phones with limited internet capabilities. This widespread accessibility has been crucial in reaching unbanked populations in Africa (GSMA, 2023) [4].

Low Barrier to Entry: USSD requires no additional app downloads or internet connection, making it user-friendly for those unfamiliar with complex technology.

Established Infrastructure: Mobile network operators already have the infrastructure in place to support USSD, minimizing additional investment needs.

WEAKNESSES OF USSD-BASED MOBILE MONEY:

Limited Functionality: USSD interactions are menu-driven and can be complex, leading to potential errors and a slow user experience compared to more modern solutions.

Data Transfer Limitations: USSD can only transfer small amounts of data, hindering the exchange of richer information that might be beneficial for future payment applications.

Limited Interoperability: Interoperability between different mobile money providers using USSD can be restricted, creating friction in seamless transactions across networks (McKinsey & Company, 2020) [2]

THE NEED FOR ALTERNATIVE SOLUTIONS:

The limitations of USSD-based mobile money highlight the need for alternative, interoperable mobile payment solutions. QR codes and USSD, when considered together, offer a promising path forward. QR codes can provide faster transactions, enhanced security features, and the ability to exchange richer data, while USSD maintains accessibility for those with feature phones. By leveraging the strengths of both technologies, Africa's mobile payment landscape can evolve to meet the demands of a growing and dynamic economy.

III. QR CODES FOR MOBILE PAYMENTS IN AFRICA: A GLIMPSE INTO THE FUTURE

QR codes, with their square, black and white patterns, offer a fast and convenient alternative to USSD for mobile payments. Scanning a QR code with a smartphone camera launches the payment process, eliminating the need for complex menu navigation. Research by Weiwei Wang (2022) in *"The Rise of QR Codes in Mobile Payments: A Global Perspective"* explores the technology's growing popularity worldwide [5]. The paper highlights advantages of QR codes, such as:

- **Ease of Use:** Scanning a QR code is a simple and intuitive process, requiring minimal technical knowledge. This makes QR codes ideal for users of all ages and technical backgrounds, promoting financial inclusion across demographics (Wang, 2022) [5].
- **Security:** QR codes can be encrypted with additional security layers, minimizing the risk of fraud compared to manually entering payment details (Singh & Singh, 2020) [6].
- **Data Encoding Capabilities:** QR codes can encode a significant amount of data beyond just payment amounts. This allows for the inclusion of additional information such as product details,

receipts, or loyalty program points (Kshetri, 2019) [7].

- **Offline Functionality (Potential):** While traditionally requiring an internet connection to process payments, advancements in QR code technology are exploring offline functionality. Static QR codes, pre-generated with payment information, can potentially facilitate transactions even in areas with limited internet access (World Bank, 2022) [8].

CHALLENGES AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR QR CODE ADOPTION IN AFRICA:

Despite their potential, QR codes face challenges in the African context:

Smartphone Dependence (Current): Currently, QR code scanning requires a smartphone camera. While smartphone penetration is steadily increasing in Africa (GSMA, 2023) [9], a significant portion of the population still relies on feature phones. This necessitates a multi-pronged approach that leverages both QR codes and USSD for an inclusive mobile payment ecosystem.

Data Consumption: Scanning QR codes incurs data usage, which can be a concern in areas with limited or expensive data plans. Optimizing QR code size and data transmission efficiency can help mitigate this challenge (Mambu, 2020) [10].

By acknowledging these challenges and exploring innovative solutions, QR codes can play a significant role in shaping Africa's mobile payment future.

IV. LEARNING FROM CHINA'S QR CODE ECOSYSTEM SUCCESS: A MODEL FOR AFRICA?

China's booming QR code payment ecosystem, dominated by platforms like Alipay and WeChat Pay, offers valuable lessons for Africa. Research by Li, J., & Xu, L. (2021). Demystifying China's QR Code Payment Dominance: A Multi-Faceted Approach. Sustainability, 13(13), 7422. identifies key drivers that fueled this remarkable growth [12]. Here's a breakdown of these drivers and their potential applicability to Africa:

Government Support: The Chinese government actively promoted QR code payments through initiatives like tax breaks and infrastructure development for digital payments. This created a supportive environment for innovation and widespread adoption. African governments can emulate this approach by offering tax incentives to merchants who adopt QR code payments and investing in expanding internet access, particularly in rural areas.

Merchant Incentives: Incentives like transaction fee reductions encouraged merchants in China to adopt QR code payments, expanding their customer base and streamlining transactions. Similarly, African governments and financial institutions can offer subsidies or reduced transaction fees for merchants who adopt QR code payments. This would

incentivize wider acceptance and encourage a shift away from cash-based transactions.

Interoperability: A key factor in China's success was the emphasis on interoperability between different platforms. This allowed users to seamlessly make payments across a vast network of merchants, regardless of the specific QR code payment platform used. Promoting open standards and fostering collaboration between mobile network operators and financial institutions in Africa can achieve similar interoperability, ensuring a user-centric and inclusive mobile payment ecosystem.

By learning from China's experience and adapting it to the unique context of Africa, stakeholders can accelerate the development of a robust QR code payment ecosystem that fosters financial inclusion and economic growth.

V. A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: QR CODES VS USSD FOR MOBILE PAYMENTS IN AFRICA

While both QR codes and USSD offer distinct advantages for mobile payments in Africa, a direct comparison can help us understand their suitability for different scenarios:

Metric	QR Codes	USSD
Accessibility	Requires smartphone (currently)	Works on virtually any phone
Security	Can be encrypted for enhanced security	Generally secure, but less robust compared to encrypted QR codes
Transaction Speed	Faster, with a single scan	Slower, with menu navigation
User Experience	Simpler and more intuitive	Can be complex and prone to errors
Data Consumption	Requires data for scanning	Minimal data consumption
Offline Functionality (Potential)	Static QR codes might work offline	Not applicable
Data Transfer Capabilities	Can encode richer data	Limited data transfer capacity

Understanding these strengths and weaknesses allows us to envision scenarios where each technology might be most beneficial:

Urban Areas with High Smartphone Penetration: QR codes can provide a fast, secure, and user-friendly payment experience for a tech-savvy population.

Rural Areas with Feature Phone Reliance: USSD, with its unparalleled accessibility, can continue to empower the unbanked and underbanked populations.

A Hybrid Approach: A future-proof strategy might involve a combination of both technologies. Static QR codes displayed at shops, combined with USSD fallback options, could cater to users with varying phone models and comfort levels.

VI. OPTIMIZING AFRICA'S MOBILE PAYMENTS: A MULTI-FACETED APPROACH

Based on the analysis, a multi-faceted approach is necessary to optimize Africa's mobile payment landscape:

PROMOTING QR CODE ADOPTION:

Government Initiatives: As discussed earlier, governments can emulate China's model by providing tax breaks and infrastructure support to encourage QR code adoption. Additionally, initiatives promoting digital literacy can help educate users about the benefits and security of QR code payments.

Smartphone Affordability: Policies promoting affordable smartphones can increase smartphone penetration, paving the way for wider QR code usage. Governments can partner with mobile network operators and device manufacturers to offer subsidized smartphones or data plans.

Public Awareness Campaigns: Educational campaigns can highlight the benefits and security of QR code payments, fostering user trust and adoption. Campaigns can leverage local media channels, community outreach programs, and partnerships with mobile network operators to reach a wider audience.

Ensuring USSD Accessibility:

Continued Network Operator Support: Mobile network operators should continue to invest in maintaining and upgrading USSD infrastructure to ensure its reliability and widespread accessibility.

USSD Menu Simplification: Streamlining USSD menus with clear and concise options can improve user experience and reduce the risk of errors. User testing and feedback can be valuable tools in refining USSD menus for optimal usability.

Integration with QR Codes: Integrating USSD fallback

options with QR code displays can provide a seamless experience for users with diverse phone models. This would allow users who lack smartphones or internet access to still make payments using USSD as a backup option.

Collaboration between stakeholders – governments, mobile network operators, financial institutions, technology providers, and NGOs – is crucial for the successful implementation of this multi-faceted approach. Each stakeholder group has a unique role to play:

Governments: As discussed previously, governments can provide a supportive environment for innovation and adoption by offering tax breaks, investing in digital infrastructure, and promoting digital literacy. Additionally, they can set regulatory frameworks that ensure security, consumer protection, and fair competition within the mobile payment ecosystem.

Mobile Network Operators (MNOs): MNOs play a critical role in providing the underlying network infrastructure for both USSD and mobile data for QR code transactions. They can invest in expanding network coverage, particularly in rural areas, and work towards reducing data costs to make mobile internet more accessible. Additionally, MNOs can collaborate with financial institutions and technology providers to develop innovative mobile payment solutions tailored to the African context.

Financial Institutions: Banks, microfinance institutions, and other financial service providers can play a key role in driving financial inclusion through mobile payments. They can develop user-friendly mobile wallets and applications that integrate with both QR codes and USSD, making it easier for individuals and businesses to participate in the formal economy. Additionally, financial institutions can offer financial literacy programs to educate users about responsible mobile payment practices.

Technology Providers: Technology providers have a crucial role in developing secure, scalable, and interoperable mobile payment solutions. They can invest in research and development to address challenges such as offline functionality for QR codes and enhanced USSD menu navigation. Additionally, technology providers can partner with other stakeholders to ensure their solutions are accessible and affordable for the African market.

NGOs: Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) can play a vital role in promoting financial inclusion and educating users, particularly in rural and underserved communities, about the benefits and security of mobile payments. They can also provide training and support to small businesses to help them adopt mobile payment solutions.

By working together, these stakeholders can create a thriving

mobile payment ecosystem in Africa that empowers individuals and businesses, fosters financial inclusion, and drives economic growth.

VII. CONCLUSION

The future of Africa's mobile payments lies in a collaborative approach that leverages the strengths of both QR codes and USSD. By promoting QR code adoption while ensuring continued USSD accessibility, stakeholders can create an inclusive and future-proof mobile payment ecosystem. This ecosystem will empower individuals across Africa to participate in the formal economy, driving financial inclusion and economic growth for the continent.

VIII. FURTHER RESEARCH

Further research and development are essential to explore advancements like:

- **Offline QR Code Functionality:** Continued exploration of technologies that enable QR code payments to function even in areas with limited internet access.
- **Enhanced USSD Menu Navigation:** Research into improved USSD menu interfaces that are more user-friendly and efficient, especially for complex transactions.
- **The Potential of Blockchain:** Investigating the potential of blockchain technology to create secure, transparent, and interoperable mobile payment solutions for Africa.

By embracing innovation and collaboration, Africa can unlock the full potential of mobile payments for its citizens and businesses, shaping a more inclusive and prosperous future.

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